

Innovative Approaches in Teaching Grammar and Literature Among Junior High School Students in Congressional District IV, Batangas Province

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Abstract

This study investigated the innovative teaching approaches employed by Junior High School teachers in Congressional District IV of Batangas Province in teaching grammar and literature. Specifically, it examined the extent of utilization of learner-centered strategies such as gamification, technology integration, collaborative learning, and other interactive approaches in enhancing students' engagement, comprehension, and motivation. The study was conducted in response to the challenges posed by traditional lecture-based instruction, declining English proficiency, low performance in international assessments such as the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), and the learning gaps identified through the Department of Education's Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning (ARAL) Program.

The study utilized a quantitative research design employing the descriptive-survey method. Data were gathered from selected Junior High School teachers and students through survey questionnaires designed to determine the extent of implementation and perceived effectiveness of innovative teaching approaches in terms of learning content, instructional activities, and assessment practices. Statistical tools were used to analyze and interpret the gathered data.

Findings revealed that innovative teaching approaches were generally utilized to a moderate to high extent and were perceived to positively influence students' participation, comprehension, and interest in grammar and literature lessons. The results further showed a significant relationship between the extent of utilization and the level of usefulness of innovative teaching approaches, indicating that increased use enhances teaching effectiveness. However, challenges such as limited instructional resources, overcrowded classrooms, insufficient technological facilities, and lack of professional training opportunities affected the consistent implementation of these strategies.

Based on the findings, the study concluded that innovative teaching approaches play a significant role in improving grammar and literature instruction among Junior High School learners. The integration of engaging, technology-supported, and collaborative strategies promotes meaningful learning experiences and supports the goals of the K to 12 Curriculum and the ARAL Program. In response to the identified needs and findings of the study, the researcher proposed the Innovative Teaching Enhancement Program (ITEP), which includes learner-centered activities, teacher training, and instructional support strategies designed to strengthen grammar proficiency, literary appreciation, communication skills, and critical thinking among learners. The study recommends the implementation of ITEP to further improve the effectiveness of grammar and literature instruction in Junior High School education.

Keywords: *innovative teaching approaches, grammar teaching, literature teaching, gamification, collaborative learning, technology integration*

Introduction

Grammar and literature are essential components of English language teaching because they help learners develop communication skills, critical thinking, creativity, and appreciation of language and culture. In today's educational setting, students learn more effectively when they are actively involved in meaningful and engaging classroom activities. Because of this, teachers are encouraged to use innovative and learner-centered approaches that make learning more interactive and enjoyable.

Traditional teaching methods alone may no longer fully address the diverse learning needs of students. Many learners experience difficulty in understanding grammar concepts and appreciating literary texts due to lack of motivation, limited exposure, and ineffective instructional practices. As education continues to evolve, teachers are expected to integrate modern teaching approaches that encourage participation, collaboration, creativity, and critical thinking.

Innovative teaching approaches such as gamification, technology integration, collaborative learning, and flipped classroom instruction have become effective strategies in improving students' engagement and comprehension. These approaches allow learners to participate actively in classroom discussions, apply grammar concepts in meaningful situations, and develop deeper understanding of literary texts.

This study aimed to determine the innovative teaching approaches utilized in teaching grammar and literature among Junior High School learners in Congressional District IV, Batangas Province. It also sought to identify the usefulness of these approaches, determine the challenges encountered by teachers, and propose enhancement activities and strategies that may improve grammar and literature instruction.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How may the extent of utilization of innovative teaching approaches be assessed by the teachers as to:

- 1.1 gamification
- 1.2 technology integration
- 1.3 collaborative learning

2. What is the level of usefulness of the innovative teaching approaches in grammar and literature lessons as assessed by the respondents in terms of:

- 2.1 learning content
- 2.2 instructional activities
- 2.3. Assessment and evaluation

3. Is there a significant relationship between the assessments on the extent of utilization and on the level of usefulness of the innovative teaching approaches?

4. What challenges are encountered by the respondents in the use of innovative teaching approaches?

5. Based on the results, what other enhancement activities may be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-quantitative research design. The descriptive method was appropriate because it focused on identifying and describing the innovative teaching approaches used by English teachers in teaching grammar and literature. It also determined the usefulness of these approaches and the challenges encountered during their implementation.

The respondents of the study were one hundred (100) English teachers from public and private secondary schools in Congressional District IV, Batangas Province. The respondents were selected through stratified random sampling to ensure proper representation from each district.

Research Instrument

The primary instrument used in gathering data was a validated researcher-made questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of items related to:

- the extent of utilization of innovative teaching approaches
- level of usefulness of innovative teaching approaches;
- challenges encountered by teachers; and
- proposed intervention activities.

The questionnaire was validated by experts in educational research and English instruction to ensure content validity and reliability.

Data Collection Procedure

The researcher first secured permission from school administrators before conducting the study. After approval was granted, the questionnaires were distributed to the respondents. The researcher personally retrieved the accomplished questionnaires and conducted interviews when necessary. The gathered data were then organized, analyzed, and interpreted.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used in analyzing the data:

- Frequency and Percentage
- Weighted Mean
- Ranking

- Pearson r Correlation

These statistical tools helped determine the extent of utilization, usefulness, relationship between variables, and challenges encountered in implementing innovative teaching approaches.

Results

1. Extent of Utilization of Innovative Teaching Approaches

1.1 Gamification

The table shows that the extent of utilization of gamification in teaching grammar and literature obtained a weighted mean of **3.43**, which was verbally interpreted as **Moderately Utilized**. This indicates that teachers sometimes used educational games, quizzes, competitions, and reward-based activities during classroom instruction. Although gamification helped increase students' motivation and participation, its utilization was not consistently practiced in all grammar and literature lessons. This implies that while gamification is recognized as an effective and engaging instructional strategy, factors such as limited time, lack of materials, and insufficient training may affect its regular implementation in the classroom.

Extent of Utilization of Innovative Teaching Approaches in terms of Gamification

The teacher...	Mean	Interpretation
1. incorporates interactive games into quizzes, and friendly competitions to make grammar and literature lessons engaging and interactive	3.50	Highly Utilized
2. uses point systems and achievement badges to recognize and motivate student's performance	3.61	Highly Utilized
3. organizes friendly competitions centered on literature and grammar to keep students engaged and involved.	3.61	Highly Utilized
4. integrate quiz-based games such as Kahoot or Quizizz (online platforms) in lessons.	3.21	Moderately Utilized
5. creates a game-based format to evaluate students' understanding and progress	3.45	Moderately Utilized
6. encourages students to design and develop their own learning games.	3.11	Moderately Utilized
7. uses story-based games to present literary elements and teach grammar in an engaging manner.	3.37	Moderately Utilized
8. incorporates puzzles and riddles connected to grammar and literature concepts to deeper understanding and spark interests.	3.48	Moderately Utilized
9. utilizes leaderboards to monitor students' progress and encourage continued motivation.	3.39	Moderately Utilized
10. find gamification helps sustain students' interest throughout the lesson.	3.54	Highly Utilized
Composite Mean	3.43	Moderately Utilized

Legend: 3.50-4.00=Highly Utilized; 2.50-3.49=Moderately Utilized; 1.50-2.49=Slightly Utilized; 1.00-1.49=Least Utilized

1.2 Technology Integration

The table reveals that the extent of utilization of technology integration in teaching grammar and literature obtained a weighted mean of **3.56**, which was verbally interpreted as **Highly Utilized**. This indicates that teachers frequently incorporated videos, multimedia presentations, online platforms, and digital instructional materials in their grammar and literature lessons. The use of technology helped make classroom instruction more interactive, engaging, and meaningful for learners. This further implies that technology integration plays an important role in improving students' comprehension, participation, and interest in learning grammar concepts and literary texts.

Extent of Utilization of Innovative Teaching Approaches in terms of Technology Integration

The teacher...	Mean	Interpretation
1. make use of digital resources and tools when presenting grammar and literature lessons.	3.63	Highly Utilized
2. uses technology to promote active participation during grammar and literature instruction.	3.60	Highly Utilized
3. connects grammar and literature concepts to real-life situations by using digital resources and online resources.	3.56	Highly Utilized
4. relates new lesson content to students' prior knowledge through the use of multimedia resources.	3.69	Highly Utilized
5. uses technology driven activities to enhance students' grammar skills and deepen their understanding of literature.	3.54	Highly Utilized
6. utilize digital tools to facilitate the analysis and understanding of literary texts.	3.49	Moderately Utilized
7. link grammar and literature lessons to online references such as articles, videos, or e-books.	3.53	Highly Utilized
8. connect classroom discussions with technology-supported activities to deepen students' comprehension.	3.52	Highly Utilized
9. facilitate student collaboration through digital platforms for group tasks and discussions.	3.48	Moderately Utilized
10. Collaborates with students and fellow teachers through technology-based collaboration to strengthen grammar and literature instructions.	3.57	Highly Utilized
Composite Mean	3.56	Highly Utilized

Legend: 3.50-4.00=Highly Utilized; 2.50-3.49=Moderately Utilized; 1.50-2.49=Slightly Utilized; 1.00-1.49=Least Utilized

1.3 Collaborative Learning

The table shows that the extent of utilization of collaborative learning in teaching grammar and literature obtained a weighted mean of **3.67**, which was verbally interpreted as **Highly Utilized**. This indicates that teachers frequently employed group discussions, peer interaction, role-playing, and cooperative learning activities during classroom instruction. Learners were given opportunities to share ideas, communicate with their classmates, and work together in accomplishing learning tasks. This implies that collaborative learning promotes active participation, improves communication skills, and enhances students' understanding of grammar concepts and literary texts through meaningful interaction and cooperation.

Extent of Utilization of Innovative Teaching Approaches in terms of Collaborative Learning

The teacher...	Mean	Interpretation
1. promote peer discussion during grammar and literature activities.	3.70	Highly Utilized
2. group students for cooperative tasks and text analysis.	3.74	Highly Utilized
3. engages students in pair or grouped tasks.	3.77	Highly Utilized
4. allows students to provide feedback on each other's work.	3.65	Highly Utilized
5. organize literature circles or reading groups.	3.58	Highly Utilized
6. encourage joint presentations of grammar and literary concepts.	3.52	Highly Utilized
7. facilitate brainstorming and group problem-solving tasks.	3.67	Highly Utilized
8. design team-based projects to assess grammar and literature learning.	3.53	Highly Utilized
9. promote a classroom culture of mutual support and respect.	3.69	Highly Utilized
10. believe that collaborative learning enhances classroom engagement.	3.80	Highly Utilized
Composite Mean	3.67	Highly Utilized

Legend: 3.50-4.00=Highly Utilized; 2.50-3.49=Moderately Utilized; 1.50-2.49=Slightly Utilized; 1.00-1.49=Least Utilized

2. Level of Usefulness of the Innovative Teaching Approaches in Grammar and Literature Lessons

2.1 Learning content

The table shows that the level of usefulness of innovative teaching approaches in terms of learning content obtained a weighted mean of **3.76**, which was verbally interpreted as **Highly Useful**. This indicates that innovative teaching approaches greatly helped students understand grammar concepts and literary texts more effectively. Teachers observed that learners became

more engaged, interested, and motivated because lessons were presented in interactive, meaningful, and learner-centered ways. This implies that the use of innovative teaching approaches enhances students' comprehension, retention of knowledge, and overall learning experiences in grammar and literature instruction.

Level of Usefulness of the Innovative Teaching Approaches in Grammar and Literature Lessons
in terms of Learning Content

The teachers'...	Mean	Interpretation
1. Innovative teaching approaches make grammar concepts easier to understand.	3.73	Highly Useful
2. approaches help students comprehend literary texts more effectively.	3.73	Highly Useful
3. lessons become more meaningful when innovative strategies are applied.	3.81	Highly Useful
4. students are able to connect grammar and literature lessons to real-life contexts.	3.79	Highly Useful
5. learning content becomes more engaging through innovative approaches.	3.79	Highly Useful
6. grammar rules are simplified using interactive methods.	3.76	Highly Useful
7. students develop a deeper understanding of themes and literary elements.	3.69	Highly Useful
8. innovative approaches help improve students' language proficiency.	3.77	Highly Useful
9. learning content becomes more organized and learner-centered.	3.80	Highly Useful
10. innovative approaches improve students' retention of grammar and literature lessons.	3.76	Highly Useful
Composite Mean	3.76	Highly Useful

Legend: 3.50-4.00=Highly Useful; 2.50-3.49=Moderately Useful; 1.50-2.49=Slightly Useful; 1.00-1.49=Least Useful

Legend: 3.50-4:00 Highly Utilized, 2.50-3.49 Moderately Utilized, 1.50-2.49 Slightly Utilized, 1.00- 1.49 Least Utilized

2.2 Instructional Activities

The table shows that the extent of utilization of artificial intelligence (AI) integration in terms of interactive and adaptive learning experiences obtained a weighted mean of 3.10, which was verbally interpreted as moderate. This indicates that AI is used to provide interactive activities and learning tasks that adjust to students' needs and abilities. This implies that AI helps create a more engaging and personalized learning environment for students. However, the moderate result suggests that the use of AI for fully adaptive and interactive instruction is still limited due to lack of resources and training.

Level of Usefulness of the Innovative Teaching Approaches in Grammar and Literature Lessons in terms of Instructional Activities

The teachers'...	Mean	Interpretation
1. innovative approaches make classroom activities more interactive.	3.80	Highly Useful
2. students actively participate in grammar and literature activities.	3.79	Highly Useful
3. learning tasks encourage collaboration among students.	3.78	Highly Useful
4. students show increased motivation during instructional activities.	3.80	Highly Useful
5. classroom discussions become more productive and meaningful.	3.83	Highly Useful
6. activities support different learning styles.	3.80	Highly Useful
7. students are more confident in completing learning tasks.	3.82	Highly Useful
8. innovative activities enhance critical and creative thinking.	3.83	Highly Useful
9. students remain attentive throughout the lesson.	3.74	Highly Useful
10. instructional activities become more enjoyable and effective.	3.83	Highly Useful
Composite Mean	3.80	Highly Useful

Legend: 3.50-4.00=Highly Useful; 2.50-3.49=Moderately Useful; 1.50-2.49=Slightly Useful; 1.00-1.49=Least Useful

2.3 Assessment and Evaluation

The table shows that instructional activities were perceived as highly useful by the respondents, as reflected by a composite mean score of 3.80. This suggests that the designed or implemented activities effectively supported learners' understanding, engagement, and participation in the learning process. The result implies that instructional activities play a significant role in enhancing students' learning experiences, particularly in reinforcing lesson content and promoting active involvement in class discussions and tasks.

Level of Usefulness of the Innovative Teaching Approaches in Grammar and Literature Lessons in terms of Assessment and Evaluation

The teachers'...	Mean	Interpretation
1. innovative approaches provide varied and appropriate assessment methods.	3.76	Highly Useful
2. assessment activities accurately measure students' understanding.	3.76	Highly Useful
3. innovative assessments allow students to demonstrate learning creatively.	3.74	Highly Useful
4. students receive timely and helpful feedback through innovative assessments.	3.76	Highly Useful
5. assessments reduce students' anxiety compared to traditional tests.	3.65	Highly Useful
6. technology-based assessments are effective in evaluating	3.68	Highly Useful

learning.

7. performance-based tasks reflect students' actual skills.	3.75	Highly Useful
8. assessment results help improve teaching and learning processes.	3.81	Highly Useful
9. students are more motivated to complete assessment tasks.	3.78	Highly Useful
10. innovative evaluation methods support continuous learning improvement.	3.85	Highly Useful

Composite Mean	3.75	Highly Useful
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Legend: 3.50-4.00=Highly Useful; 2.50-3.49=Moderately Useful; 1.50-2.49=Slightly Useful; 1.00-1.49=Least Useful

3. Relationship between the Assessments on the Extent of Utilization and on the Level of Usefulness of the Innovative Approaches

Significant Relationship between the Assessment on the Extent of Utilization and on the Level of Usefulness of the Innovative Approaches in terms of Learning Content

The table presents the significant relationship between the assessment on the extent of utilization and the level of usefulness of innovative teaching approaches in grammar and literature lessons in terms of learning content among Junior High School students in Congressional District IV, Batangas Province. The results revealed that all variables showed statistically significant relationships, indicating that the degree to which innovative approaches were utilized was associated with teachers' perceptions of their usefulness in improving learning content. The findings suggested that greater implementation of innovative strategies corresponded to higher perceived usefulness in making grammar and literature content meaningful, organized, and engaging.

Extent of Utilization	r-value	Degree of Relationship	p-value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Gamification	0.534	Strong	0.000	Reject	Significant
Technology Integration	0.431	Moderate	0.000	Reject	Significant
Collaborative Learning	0.582	Strong	0.000	Reject	Significant

Legend: Coefficient of correlation (r): +1.0 (Perfect relationship), +.76 to .99 (Very Strong relationship), +.51 to .75 (Strong relationship), +.26-.50 (Moderate Relationship), +.11 to .25 (Weak relationship), +.01 to .10 (Very weak relationship), .00 (No relationship)

Relationship between the Assessment on the Extent of Utilization and on the Level of Usefulness of the Innovative Approaches in terms of Instructional Activities

The table shows that there is a significant relationship between the extent of utilization and the level of usefulness of innovative teaching approaches in terms of instructional activities. This indicates that higher utilization of innovative strategies is associated with higher perceived

usefulness in enhancing instructional activities. It further implies that as teachers consistently implement these approaches, students' engagement, interaction, and learning effectiveness in grammar and literature lessons also improve.

Extent of Utilization	r-value	Degree of Relationship	p-value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Gamification	0.454	Moderate	0.000	Reject	Significant
Technology Integration	0.371	Moderate	0.000	Reject	Significant
Collaborative Learning	0.59	Strong	0.000	Reject	Significant

Legend: Coefficient of correlation (r): +1.0 (Perfect relationship), +.76 to .99 (Very Strong relationship), +.51 to .75 (Strong relationship), +.26-.50 (Moderate Relationship), +.11 to .25 (Weak relationship), +.01 to .10 (Very weak relationship), .00 (No relationship)

Significant Relationship between the Assessment on the Extent of Utilization and on the Level of Usefulness of the Innovative Approaches in terms of Instructional Activities

The table shows that there is a significant relationship between the extent of utilization and the level of usefulness of innovative approaches in terms of instructional activities, indicating that higher utilization of innovative teaching strategies is associated with higher perceived usefulness in classroom instruction. This suggests that as teachers more frequently apply these approaches, instructional activities become more engaging, interactive, and effective in supporting students' learning in grammar and literature lessons.

Extent of Utilization	r-value	Degree of Relationship	p-value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Gamification	0.457	Moderate	0.000	Reject	Significant
Technology Integration	0.425	Moderate	0.000	Reject	Significant
Collaborative Learning	0.661	Strong	0.000	Reject	Significant

Legend: Coefficient of correlation (r): +1.0 (Perfect relationship), +.76 to .99 (Very Strong relationship), +.51 to .75 (Strong relationship), +.26-.50 (Moderate Relationship), +.11 to .25 (Weak relationship), +.01 to .10 (Very weak relationship), .00 (No relationship)

3. Challenges Encountered by the Respondents in the Use of Innovative Teaching Approaches in Teaching Grammar and Literature

The table shows that teachers **strongly agree** that they encounter challenges in using innovative teaching approaches in teaching grammar and literature, as reflected by the mean score of **3.56**. This indicates that despite recognizing the usefulness of strategies such as gamification, technology integration, collaborative learning, and other learner-

centered approaches, teachers still face certain difficulties in their implementation. These challenges may include limited instructional resources, time constraints, lack of training, classroom management issues, and varying student readiness for interactive activities. Overall, the result implies that while innovative approaches are valued in improving teaching and learning, addressing these challenges is necessary to ensure their more effective and consistent use in grammar and literature instruction.

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. Limited access to technology and reliable internet connectivity restricts the effective implementation of innovative teaching approaches.	3.54	Strongly Agree
2. Students' difficulty in adapting to changes brought about by innovative teaching strategies affects their engagement and participation.	3.48	Agree
3. Insufficient classroom management styles limit the effective implementation of innovative instructional approaches.	3.56	Strongly Agree
4. A lack of resources limits the effective use of creative and technology-based teaching approaches.	3.63	Strongly Agree
5. Large class sizes make it difficult to implement interactive and learner-centered methods effectively.	3.56	Strongly Agree
6. Technological disruptions and system malfunctions occur during technology-based lessons, affecting the continuity of instruction.	3.63	Strongly Agree
7. Technological inadequacy among teachers affects the effective integration of innovative teaching strategies.	3.64	Strongly Agree
8. Not all lessons are suitable for certain innovative or technology-integrated teaching approaches.	3.41	Agree
9. The modes of assessment techniques and evaluation in innovative learning environments present challenges in accurately measuring student performance.	3.49	Agree
10. The need for continuous curriculum review poses challenges in aligning innovative practices with prescribed standards and learning competencies. Balancing innovation with curriculum requirements is difficult.	3.66	Strongly Agree
Composite Mean	3.56	Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.50-4.00=Strongly Agree; 2.50-3.49=Agree; 1.50-2.49=Disagree; 1.00-1.49=Strongly Disagree

4. Proposed Enhancement Activities

The Innovative Teaching Enhancement Program (ITEP) is designed to strengthen the implementation of innovative teaching approaches in teaching grammar and literature among Junior High School learners.

- Teacher Capability Building Program – Conduct regular training, seminars, and Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions to enhance teachers’ skills in using gamification, technology integration, and collaborative learning strategies effectively in classroom instruction.
- Instructional Materials Development Initiative – Develop and provide updated and interactive instructional materials such as worksheets, modules, digital resources, and activity-based tasks that support engaging grammar and literature lessons.
- Technology Integration Strengthening Program – Improve access to ICT tools and encourage the consistent use of multimedia presentations, online learning platforms, and educational applications to enhance teaching and learning experiences.
- Collaborative and Interactive Learning Enhancement Activities – Promote learner-centered classroom strategies such as group activities, peer tutoring, role-playing, and performance-based tasks to increase student participation, communication skills, and comprehension.

Discussion

The findings of the study showed that English teachers highly utilized innovative teaching approaches such as gamification, technology integration, and collaborative learning in teaching grammar and literature. Teachers observed that these strategies encouraged active participation, increased students’ motivation, and improved classroom interaction.

Gamification activities such as educational games, quizzes, and competitions made grammar lessons more enjoyable and engaging for students. Technology integration through videos, presentations, and online learning tools enhanced students’ understanding of lessons and increased their interest in learning. Collaborative learning activities such as group discussions, role-playing, and peer interaction also helped students improve their communication skills and literary interpretation.

The study further revealed that innovative teaching approaches were highly useful in improving learning content, instructional delivery, and assessment practices. Students became more confident in expressing ideas, participating in discussions, and analyzing literary texts.

Moreover, a significant relationship was found between the extent of utilization and the usefulness of innovative teaching approaches. This indicates that the more these approaches are applied in the classroom, the more beneficial they become to students’ learning experiences.

Despite the positive effects of innovative teaching approaches, teachers encountered several challenges during implementation. These included lack of instructional materials, limited technological resources, insufficient training, overcrowded classrooms, and time constraints. These challenges affected the full implementation of innovative instructional strategies in grammar and literature classes.

Based on the findings, enhancement activities and strategies were proposed. These include teacher training programs, development of technology-based instructional materials, collaborative classroom activities, gamified learning tasks, and continuous professional development opportunities for teachers.

Conclusion

In light of the foregoing findings, the following conclusions are drawn.

1. The assessment on the utilization of innovative teaching approaches in grammar and literature was moderately utilized in gamification, while highly utilized in technology integration and collaborative learning.
2. The level of the innovative teaching approaches was assessed in learning content, instructional activities and assessment and evaluation was highly useful in grammar and literature lessons.
3. The assessments on the extent of utilization and on the level of usefulness of the innovative approaches were found significantly related in all pairs of variables.
4. The common challenges of teachers are need for continuous curriculum review, that will align innovative practices with prescribed standards and learning competencies, technological inadequacy among teachers, lack of resources and technological disruptions and system malfunctions.
5. Enhancement activities after lobbying to the higher authorities maybe proposed.

Recommendations:

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn from the collected data, the researcher recommends the following:

1. The proposed engaging activities may be presented to the authorities for an in-depth evaluation, approval, and possible use in Congressional District IV.
2. The implementation and application of the proposed innovative approaches activities may be utilized by the involved and concerned personnel.
3. Teachers, together with the administrations, may work together in overcoming the encountered challenges in relation to innovative approaches in teaching grammar and literature.
4. Future researchers may use the results of this study as a springboard in conducting a similar or parallel study to ensure comprehensive view of the innovative approaches in teaching in other learning areas in Congressional District IV, Batangas Province.

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